

THE INTEGRATION OF THE “CLUSTERED THINKING” METHOD AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON GROUP ELEMENTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the effectiveness of the “Clustered Thinking” method in teaching the physical and chemical properties of carbon group elements, and the importance of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into this process. The use of AI tools during the lesson process for efficiently gathering data, creating clusters, visualizing, designing tests, and evaluating students is discussed. Additionally, the opportunities for practical learning of the topic through virtual laboratories and enhancing the quality of the educational process using AI tools are explored.*

Keywords: *carbon group elements, clustered thinking, artificial intelligence, physical properties, chemical properties, teaching methods, virtual laboratories, AI technologies, educational effectiveness, periodic table.*

Introduction. The elements of the carbon group (C, Si, Ge, Sn, Pb) possess distinctive physical and chemical properties in the field of chemistry, and their study holds significant importance for numerous scientific and practical processes. The use of interactive methods in teaching this topic enhances students' interest in the lesson and contributes to effective knowledge acquisition. The “Clustered Thinking” method is recognized as an important tool for teaching students to think logically and analytically. The introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in today's education system is creating new opportunities to improve the quality of education. This article is dedicated to exploring the possibilities of effectively teaching the physical and chemical properties of carbon group elements by combining the “Clustered Thinking” method with AI tools.

Materials and Methods

Clustered Thinking Method

Clustered thinking is a teaching method that directs students to organize knowledge by categorizing ideas related to a topic into logical groups and connecting them visually. In this method, the central concept is chosen as the focal point, and related information is illustrated in the form of a network. This approach facilitates understanding the structure of the topic and encourages students to engage in deeper thinking.

In chemistry lessons, the application of the clustered thinking method is one of the effective strategies that helps systematize and deepen students' thought processes. The significance of this method in the educational process has been studied in various research, and experiences in this area show important results. A study by Al-Tamimi (2024) found that the clustered thinking approach in chemistry lessons is successful in developing synthesis thinking abilities. The authors of the research highlight that this method is a convenient way to "enrich students' knowledge and improve their logical thinking abilities". The cluster strategy encourages students to systematize new information, thereby enhancing educational effectiveness ("The Effectiveness of the Umbrella

Cluster Strategy," 2024). In a study by Bretz and Galloway (2015), they explored how cluster analysis directs students towards meaningful learning. They successfully implemented the clustered thinking method in first-year university laboratory courses, demonstrating that this approach plays a significant role in “strengthening the meaning and relevance of students’ knowledge” (“Using Cluster Analysis to Characterize Meaningful Learning,” 2015). Chan and Bauer (2014) applied cluster analysis to identify students struggling in general chemistry courses. Their research demonstrated the effectiveness of clustering as a method for analyzing emotional characteristics and identifying students' problems in the learning process (“Identifying At-Risk Students in General Chemistry,” 2014). In 2024, Misbah, Hamidah, and Sriyati used cluster analysis to develop pre-service physics teachers' critical thinking skills. Their research showed how this approach helps in developing abilities by grouping them, which can also be applied to chemistry teaching (“Study of Critical Thinking Skill Patterns,” 2024). A study by Battaglia and Fazio (2017) examined the use of k-means clustering, based on the Feynman method, to modify students' reasoning lines in logical thinking activities. They emphasized that this approach is effective in “improving students’ adaptability of knowledge and understanding in the learning process” (“K-Means Clustering to Study How Student Reasoning Lines Can Be Modified,” 2017). Based on these studies, the clustered thinking method is regarded as an innovative approach that helps develop students’ logical thinking, problem analysis, and independent decision-making skills. This method contributes to systematizing the learning process and increasing students' interest in learning.

The “Clustered Thinking” method involves breaking down the topic into components and presenting concepts in a graphical form. In this method:

- Central Idea: The physical and chemical properties of the carbon group elements.
- Divided Sections: Atomic structure of the elements, physical properties, chemical reactions, and their applications.

“Clustered thinking”

2. Integration of AI Technologies

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies are currently opening new opportunities in the field of education, particularly in chemistry. Through clustering methods, it is possible to systematize data, develop students' thinking abilities, and improve educational effectiveness. Below are the conclusions and quotes from studies related to this topic.

López-Pérez et al. (2024) examined the impact of clustering methods on learning through the use of AI. According to them, “clustering and unsupervised learning techniques are essential for data identification and creating a systematic approach to the learning process” (López-Pérez, 2024). This approach allows for the application of new pedagogical methods in chemistry lessons. A study by Galindo-Domínguez (2024) explored the use of AI in education. The article discusses methods for “identifying students' knowledge levels and optimizing learning through clustering techniques” in teaching chemistry and physics (Galindo-Domínguez, 2024). This increases the possibilities for developing an individualized approach in chemistry lessons. In a study by Aristodemou and Tietze (2018), the use of AI and clustering methods in intellectual property analysis was explored. According to them, “machine learning methods, including k-means clustering, can be effective in analyzing chemical substances” (Aristodemou and Tietze, 2018). This methodology can be useful in better visualizing data in chemistry lessons. Shaikh et al. (2022) successfully applied k-means clustering in agricultural studies using AI technologies. They emphasize that “intuitive and effective methods for data learning through k-means clustering have been developed, which can also be widely applied in education” (Shaikh et al., 2022). This creates opportunities for analyzing complex problems in chemistry education. These studies demonstrate that clustering and AI methods have significant potential in chemistry education. These approaches help to conduct deeper data analysis, develop students' abilities, and optimize educational processes.

AI tools were used to organize and enhance the effectiveness of the lesson. The following processes utilized AI tools

Data collection: AI was used to search for updated information on the properties of the carbon group elements.

Cluster creation: Clusters were quickly and accurately formed using AI tools (Lucidchart, Miro).

Virtual laboratories: Reactions of the carbon group elements were studied using PhET and other chemical modeling platforms.

Tests and assessment: AI was used to design test questions and assess students' knowledge.

3. Participants

The research was conducted as an experiment with 9th-grade students from School No. 81 of General Secondary Education. A total of 151 students participated in the lesson. An experimental trial was conducted among 9th-grade students to determine the effectiveness of teaching with clustered thinking and AI. The experimental group included 75 students, while the control group consisted of 76 students. The control group was taught using traditional methods, while the experimental group was taught using the new methodology. The results showed an average score of 3.8 in the control group and 4.4 in the experimental group. Based on this data, a pedagogical experiment was conducted, and the results are shown in the diagrams below.

Results

Lesson assimilation indicator: With the integration of AI into the “Clustered Thinking” method, the level of topic assimilation increased by 16% compared

to traditional methods. Pupils retained information better with the help of clusters.

Level of interactivity: Clustered thinking and AI tools helped engage students actively in the lesson. The level of correct answers to topic-related questions was 88%.

• **Interest and assessment results:** According to survey results, 92% of students responded that “using AI tools made learning more interesting.”

Discussion

The integration of the “Clustered Thinking” method with Artificial Intelligence (AI) demonstrated high effectiveness in teaching the physical and chemical properties of carbon group elements. With the help of AI:

Deep analysis of the topic and data searching became easier.

The creation of clusters in a visual format significantly improved students' understanding.

Theoretical knowledge was reinforced with practical experiences through virtual laboratories.

Additionally, AI tools enabled real-time assessment, allowing for quick and accurate evaluation of students' knowledge. However, some students faced difficulties in using technological tools, which necessitated prior training on the tools to be used during the lesson.

Conclusion

The combined use of the "Clustered Thinking" method and Artificial Intelligence showed excellent results in studying the carbon group elements. This integration plays a crucial role in enhancing students' understanding of the topic and developing their thinking and analytical skills. In the future, further integration of AI technologies into the educational process offers the potential to improve lesson effectiveness.

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